

On the impact of Lithium Diffusion on the Neutron Activation of Alumina Coatings in the DEMO WCLL Breeding Blanket

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ABSTRACT

Thin amorphous alumina protective coatings are one of the most promising solutions for mitigating the corrosion, tritium permeation, and magnetohydrodynamic instability affecting PbLi within the Water-Cooled Lithium Lead (WCLL) breeding blanket planned for the European demonstration reactor DEMO. However, the diffusion of lithium within the coatings and the consequent formation of ternary compounds could alter both their structural integrity and their behaviour under neutron irradiation. In this work, a Monte Carlo model of the WCLL breeding blanket is developed using the OpenMC code, with a completely toroidal geometry, to evaluate the neutron activation of both pure and lithium-enriched alumina coatings. After implicit validation of the model through the calculation of neutron flux, Tritium Breeding Ratio (TBR), and radiation damage, the activation and decay analysis is conducted assuming constant reaction rates. The results show significant differences between the two types of coating in terms of specific activity over time after shutdown: in particular, the presence of lithium significantly increases the production of long-lived radionuclides, modifying both the temporal evolution and the potential classification of waste according to international standards for the management of irradiated materials. The analysis highlights the importance of an in-depth characterization of lithium diffusion mechanisms and their impact on the neutron response of coatings, providing useful information for the design of highly durable protective barriers in the extreme environment of fusion reactors.

Keywords: DEMO WCLL breeding blanket, Alumina coatings, Activation analysis, Lithium diffusion

1. INTRODUCTION

Many of the latest concepts of breeding blanket foreseen for the DEMO fusion reactor, namely the last intermediate step of the European agenda towards large-scale electricity production from nuclear fusion, are based on an eutectic mixture of molten lithium and lead, usually referred to as 'PbLi'. The blanket is supposed to breed tritium by reacting with the neutrons produced by fusion reactions within the plasma, as well as absorbing the neutron energy and yielding it to secondary systems for electricity production.

However, many technological challenges arise from the interaction of PbLi with the structural materials in the blanket: in particular, the present designs foresee the use of Reduced-Activation Ferritic-Martensitic (RAFM) steels, due to the low amount of nuclear waste they are expected to produce and to the lower extent of swelling phenomena and helium embrittlement, especially in comparison

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with austenitic steels, whose high content of nickel is damaging in this regard. The reference choice of RAFM steel in the breeding blanket is EUROFER97, whose main alloying elements - besides iron - are chromium (8.5-9.5 wt.%) and tungsten (1.0-1.2 wt.%) [1]. Detrimental effects due to the lithium-lead eutectic in the blanket include the formation of helium bubbles, which hinder the removal of heat from the breeder, magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) instabilities to the PbLi flow in the loop pipes, the permeation of tritium into the cooling system (and possibly to the environment) and, above all, corrosion [2]. For corrosion, a strong dissolution of the metal is observed, in which the alloying elements migrate towards the interface with the breeder, giving rise to a mass flux which is proportional to the solubility of the elements in PbLi. The EUROFER consumption in the system is estimated to be up to 200 μm per year [2], and it is enhanced by the temperature and the velocity of the PbLi flow.

A promising solution to the aforementioned technological issues is the application of protective coatings on structural materials: in this respect, amorphous/nanocrystalline alumina ($a - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) is regarded as a reference choice. Indeed, excellent performances by this material are extensively reported in the literature: from the standpoint of tritium permeation, the presence of a micrometric $a - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ coating is observed to reduce the mass flux of hydrogen isotopes on EUROFER by a factor higher than 10^5 [3]. Furthermore, excellent mechanical properties are observed in this material, with quite high mechanical strength (elastic module of 195.4 ± 8.7 GPa and a hardness around 10 GPa [4]), and, above all, a plastic behavior which is uncommon for ceramic materials [4][5]. The stability of amorphous alumina under irradiation was also extensively studied: as a result, an increased Young's modulus and an enhanced fracture toughness can be noticed, due to the grain growth induced by the radiation damage [6].

As far as the corrosion resistance is concerned, coatings exposed to PbLi at 550°C were able to maintain their nominal thickness and to fully protect EUROFER even after 8000 h of exposure [3]. However, the contact with lithium undermines the stability of lithium: the highly reducing nature of the latter makes the formation of ternary compounds, like lithium aluminate, more thermodynamically favorable than Al_2O_3 . The mechanism of Li diffusion into the coating is yet to be properly characterized, but recent Monte Carlo simulations have shown peaks in the Li concentration (up to 14 at.%) at the interface with EUROFER [7]. This issue may significantly affect the protection of the substrate, and the activity of lithium under irradiation may induce severe damage to the coating.

In this paper, the behavior of alumina coatings under neutron irradiation is analyzed, with particular attention to the implications of lithium diffusion. In order to do so, an OpenMC [8] Monte Carlo neutron transport model of the DEMO Water-Cooled Lithium Lead (WCLL) breeding blanket is used to obtain the neutron flux and cross-sections within the component, in order to evaluate the activation of the coating material. The specific activity of the coatings is computed up to 1,000 years after the DEMO reactor shutdown, following 5 full-power years of operation.

1.1. Alumina Coating Properties

An effective procedure for the production of amorphous alumina coatings is the one proposed by the startup X-nano at the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT). These coatings are realised by Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD). As outlined by Di Fonzo et al. [9], a compact, uniform film can be obtained below 1 Pa, while for higher values a columnar structure and then an open microstructure are observed, with decreasing density and growing oxygen-to-aluminium ratio. The standard density values of these PLD coatings are around 3.57 g/cm^3 , and the nominal thickness that is usually considered is 3 μm , which guarantees excellent performances with respect to the permeation of hydrogen isotopes [3]. Thermal annealing treatments performed at the IIT laboratories on the coatings show - from the corresponding XRD patterns - that the amorphous structure of alumina is maintained for temperatures up to 600°C.

2. NEUTRONICS MODELING OF THE DEMO WCLL BREEDING BLANKET

On the basis of the collected data about the properties of the alumina coatings, a model of the DEMO WCLL (Water-Cooled Lithium Lead) breeding blanket was built with the open-source Monte Carlo particle-transport code OpenMC [8].

In many of the latest simulations of the breeding blanket, a Single-Module-Segment (SMS) approach is adopted to determine the geometry. Specifically, a basic elementary unit of the blanket - the 'slice' - is replicated all over the poloidal cross-section, creating radial shells with a specific material composition. For the model proposed in this paper, the radial segmentation was taken from the model elaborated by Moro and others [10] using MCNP [11]. In the present model, a fully toroidal structure is considered, while the aforementioned references [10],[12], like many other examples in literature, feature only a toroidal segment extending from 10° to 20° . The final structure of the OpenMC model, with the relative zones, is shown in Figure 1: the poloidal cross-section is the result of a simplified geometry, built by connecting two semi-ellipses representing the Inboard (IB) and Outboard (OB) zones.

A fundamental point for the model is clearly the presence of the coatings: their application concerns the first wall, the back plate, and the pipes, hence any surface in contact with PbLi. The idea that was followed for the model was the addition of more radial sectors representing the coatings, which were placed after the last sectors of the first wall and of the breeding zone, and before the back plate: the coatings in these zones were also referred to as 1, 2, and 3, respectively, both for the Inboard and the Outboard.

The main purpose of the OpenMC simulation was the assessment of the specific activities of the coating materials. Before performing these simulations, an indirect validation of the model was carried out by determining three relevant quantities for the breeding blanket: the neutron flux, the Tritium Breeding Ratio (TBR) and the radiation damage, expressed in displacements per atom (dpa). The feasibility of OpenMC in this regard has been proven in the last years for fusion systems, including the breeding blankets. For example, a recent article by Zhang et al. [13] showed a comparison between the tritium breeding calculations performed with OpenMC and with the widely used and validated MCNP transport code: the relative deviation between the TBR values obtained by the two codes for a Li_2O blanket was estimated to be around 0.02%.

The representation of the plasma source was implemented in OpenMC using the Python package `openmc_plasma_source`, which contains different shapes of neutron source for fusion applications: specifically, the `tokamak_source` function was used, which allowed to obtain a 50%-Deuterium-50%-Tritium plasma [14]. The same plasma parameters as in [10] were used: in particular, the major and minor radius were 907.2 cm and 292.7 cm, respectively, the triangularity was 0.33 and the elongation 1.59. This plasma configuration determined a neutron source strength of $7.232 \cdot 10^{20}$ n/s and a predicted thermal power of 2037 MW [10]. For the materials in the model, the cross-sections were taken from the ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear data dictionary; the temperature of the breeder was approximated to 900 K.

The Tritium Breeding Ratio inside the blanket was obtained using an OpenMC tally, with the score (`H3-production`); the tally was applied to all the cells of the breeding zone and of the PbLi manifolds, and it was distinguished between the Inboard and Outboard segments; a filter was set in order to consider the contributions coming only from Li-6 and Li-7. The overall mean value, obtained from the sum over the considered cells, was determined to be 1.13456 ± 0.00114 , which differs by 0.14% from the result (1.133) obtained in [10], and it is compatible with the current target values for DEMO.

For the flux, the values in the OB zone were in agreement with the reference, with a decrease by two orders of magnitude over the blanket from the $6 \cdot 10^{14}$ n/($\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$) at the armour. A higher flux than found in literature was instead obtained in the outermost zones of the Inboard segment, with an increase through the back-supporting structure being witnessed. A plausible explanation for this behaviour lies in the present model not featuring toroidal field coils, especially the central solenoid inside the torus: this absence would in fact enhance neutron leakages from one side to the other in the Inboard segment,

thereby increasing the flux in those zones, since no neutron absorption would occur. This preliminary justification needs to be corroborated by the actual addition of a central solenoid to the present model.

As a further confirmation of the validity of the model, the radiation damage to structural materials was computed by considering the Norgett, Robinson, and Torrens (NRT) formula, as a correction to the Kinchin-Pease model [15]. Similar results to the reference models were obtained [10], with the dpa after 1 full-power year going from 10 at the first wall to 10^{-2} at the back-supporting structure, except for the overestimated IB outer zones discussed above.

In order to obtain relative statistical uncertainties of the analyzed quantities below 1%, it was necessary to run simulations with at least 10^6 simulated source particles.

3. ACTIVATION ANALYSIS

The activation analysis of the coatings was carried out using the 'Predictor integrator' algorithm from `openmc_deplete`, and using an 'Independent operator', which performs a single transport simulation and then assumes constant flux and microscopic cross-sections. This is a quite fast approach, but an almost necessary one, since the complexity of the model would have made these calculations too computationally demanding: a more accurate alternative would in fact require the use of a 'Coupled Operator', which performs multiple neutron transport simulations and updates the reaction rates by recalculating the flux and the cross-sections at each timestep [16]. Nonetheless, the use of a transport-independent operator is a suitable choice in fusion systems, since the neutron source spectrum in the plasma is independent of the composition of the structural materials, and the depletion of the latter does not significantly alter the neutron flux and spectrum in the blanket. As such, this assumption provides reasonable values for the specific radioactivity. Simulations with 100,000 neutron source particles were carried out.

In order to retrieve the elemental composition of the alumina coatings after lithium diffusion, for the construction of the corresponding OpenMC material, the density of pure alumina was considered and the atomic concentration of lithium in the layer was set to be equal to the one in the breeder, namely $5.04 \cdot 10^{21}$ at/cm³. With this simplified approach, the lithium atomic fraction in the coating was estimated to be 4.58%. This choice assumed a uniform concentration of lithium in the film, so it did not account for the aforementioned peaks at the interface with EUROFER. The calculated profiles of the specific activity as a function of time after the shutdown are reported in Figure 2.

The definition of assessment criteria for coating activation followed the study conducted by Gilbert and others [17], who predicted the amount of nuclear waste created in the DEMO reactor, considering the WCLL, HCLL and HCPB blanket concepts. The authors considered a categorization according to the limits defined by the UKAEA on the IAEA waste classes. In particular, a main distinction was established between Low Level Waste (LLW) and Intermediate Level Waste (ILW): the limit between the two categories corresponds to an α -activity lower than 4 kBq/g and a combined $\beta + \gamma$ activity no higher than 12 kBq/g. In OpenMC, the subdivision of the activity into the different decay schemes is not straightforward: therefore, this model distinguished LLW and ILW by setting the 12-kBq/g threshold to the whole specific activity. This choice was not conservative towards the α -activity, yet it derived from arguing that the nuclides foreseen to be relevant in the system, namely Al-26 and H-3, decay β ; additionally, no impurities were assumed in the coatings, so the presence of long-lived heavy α -emitters was excluded.

The coatings applied on the First Wall required more than 1,000 years to decay below the LLW limit; the other Inboard protective layers reached this condition within a millennium, while, at the corresponding Outboard positions, the films without any lithium achieved the goal in less than 100 years (Table I). The significant difference in the activation that was observed for corresponding Inboard and Outboard positions is consistent with the aforementioned overestimation of the IB flux.

In all the zones, the coatings containing lithium were regularly the most activated. On the other hand,

Figure 1. Poloidal cross-section (left) and half toroidal cross-section (right) of the WCLL breeding blanket model created in OpenMC. The following blanket zones are reported in the image: tungsten armour, first wall, breeding zones (red), PbLi manifolds (pink), back plate, water manifolds (blue), back-supporting structure (grey), and vacuum vessel (orange).

in the long term the specific activities of both types of coatings tended to converge to similar values: this was considered to be symptomatic of the dominance of tritium activity (in Li-containing coatings) up to the first hundred years, while for the following period the major contribution was expected to come from Al-26 (with a half-life of $7.17 \cdot 10^5$ years).

Table I. Waste categorization of the alumina coatings, with and without lithium diffusion, after 100 years from the reactor shutdown, and the relative specific activities (kBq/g)

Coating		IB1	IB2	IB3	OB1	OB2	OB3
Alumina w/o Li (Al_2O_3)	Category	ILW	ILW	ILW	ILW	LLW	LLW
	kBq/g	724	48	40	1,181	6	4
Alumina with Li ($Al_2O_3 + Li$)	Category	ILW	ILW	ILW	ILW	ILW	ILW
	kBq/g	866,534	101,192	572,529	1,455,073	30,150	93,511

Figure 2. Profiles of the specific activities of the alumina coatings with and without the diffusion of lithium, in the various zones of the breeding blanket. The horizontal line in each graph represents the previously described specific activity threshold of 12 kBq/g .

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work analyzes the neutron activation of alumina coatings intended for the Water-Cooled Lithium Lead (WCLL) breeding blanket of the European demonstration reactor DEMO. Particular attention was paid to the effects associated with lithium diffusion within the coating. The analyses were conducted using a fully toroidal Monte Carlo model of the WCLL breeding blanket with OpenMC, implicitly validated by comparing neutron fluxes, the Tritium Breeding Ratio (TBR), and radiation damage with reference results found in the literature. The activation analysis, based on an independent operator, highlighted significant differences between pure alumina coatings and those contaminated with lithium. In particular, the presence of lithium significantly increases the specific activity in the medium to long term after shutdown, with greater production of long-lived radionuclides and a potentially significant impact on waste classification according to international standards. This result suggests that the diffusion of lithium in coatings, already known for the possible formation of harmful ternary compounds, is also a critical factor from the point of view of radiation protection and the management of irradiated material. The study highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary characterization of the behavior of alumina coatings, including thermochemical, structural, and neutron phenomena. Future developments will focus on the introduction of more accurate models of lithium diffusion, the use of fully coupled depletion operators, comparative analysis with other promising coating materials for fusion reactor applications, and the design of appropriate experimental campaigns to validate the material in the reactor.

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